

CHALLENGES OF OUT-OF-SCHOOL CHILDREN IN NIGERIA: THE IMPLICATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Sustainable Development is a gradual process of quality change and the creation of conditions for sustaining that change for the present and future generation, while Education is an essential instrument for developing the needed skills, attitudes, and the production of new knowledge for the attainment of sustainable development. Despite the expected role and relevance of education, one begins to wonder as to why Nigeria continues to record a high rate of out-of-school children. The consequences of these have obvious impacts on individuals and society. Children who are out of school are exposed to social stigma, fewer job opportunities, lower salaries, higher probability of involvement in criminal activities and others which could result in the poor economic, socio-political and environmental well-being of the population. It is on these notes that the study examined the challenges of Out-of-School Children in Nigeria and the implications for sustainable development. The rising number of out-of-school children in Nigeria has a great implication on the achievement of sustainable development in Nigeria. Hence, it is recommended among others that there is need for the government to reduce the cost of education by eliminating school fees at all levels of education, providing cash transfers, and strengthening the fight against poverty, insecurity, child trafficking, gender discrimination; establish more schools and come up with a national policy to address the issue of Almajiri and nomadic children education to resolve issues of Out-of-School children in Nigeria.

Keywords: Education, Access to Education, Out-of-School-Children, Development, Sustainable Development

Introduction

Lack of access to education is a violation of human rights which amounts to denial of learning opportunities and skills

development and paves the way for potential increases of abuse, exploitation, and recruitment to unscrupulous groups and promotes all forms of threat to national

peace. Lack of access to education is also synonymous with denial of access to meaningful employment, and a leading cause of perpetual intergenerational poverty and inequality, significant loss in the labour force and drawbacks for the development of the nation. Hence, no child of school age should be denied access to quality education. That is why Musa et al, (2019) acknowledged that Education, be it formal or non-formal is regarded as an important tool for achieving national objectives. There is no doubt that the rate of out-of-school children in Nigeria is a great challenge to the achievement of sustainable development in Nigeria and so, needs urgent attention. No wonder the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), in the National Policy on Education acknowledged that no nation can achieve economic, social and technological progress and self-sufficiency without a good system of education. Defective education can be a major threat to security, peaceful coexistence, economy and governance in any part of the world. This can be one of the reasons why education is regarded as a powerful agent of social transformation. It does not only act as a means to sustainable development in a society but also increases the rate of such development.

The most recent estimations of out-of-school children confirmed by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) in September 2023, put the number of out-of-school children in Nigeria at about 20 million, (Guardian, 2023).

The scorecard of Nigeria's school children is an indication that Nigeria lags in the race towards achieving sustainable development as the country records the highest number of Out-Of-School Children in the world. In an attempt to tackle the challenges of achieving sustainable development worldwide, the United Nations Member States, in 2015 adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable

Development which outlines a blueprint to address global challenges across a broad range of themes including poverty, health, education, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace and justice (United Nations, 2015). It is evident that the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations depend solely on the kind of education individuals, communities and nations are exposed to at any period. This is because education is the major factor in ensuring change in attitude, skills and acquisition of new knowledge. In essence, it is a process by which individuals within a particular community improve their well-being and that of their community. That is why Fafunwa (2008) described education as the engine that drives the development of any nation. This is arguably the basis for the inclusion of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4) which focuses on the provision of access and equity to quality education among the development goals of the United Nation's agenda targeted at 2030.

It is against this backdrop that the study tends to examine the challenges of out-of-school children in Nigeria: and the implication on sustainable development. Profoundly, the findings of this research should stimulate policy efforts towards reducing Out-of-School-Children (OOSC) and ensuring that every child in Nigeria has access to education, providing them the opportunity to maximize their economic and social potential by exploring the environmental resources in a manner that ensures sustainable development.

Conceptual Clarifications

Access to Education

Wikipedia describes universal access to education as the ability of all people to have equal opportunity in education, regardless of their social class, race, gender, sexuality, ethnic background or physical and mental

disabilities. This definition is by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1984, which themed access to education as the right of everyone to education. Access to education can further be described as the state whereby every individual is free from any form of hindrance to the right to enrol, attend and complete the prescribed programme of study. Thus, Okeke (2009) in Ikiyei et al (2022) see a lack of access to education as a lack of opportunity to enrol in an educational institution and complete the prescribed programme of study without dropping out; and the lack of opportunities to transit to the next level of education. It is the responsibility of the government to provide and ensure every citizen receives education. Thus, no child should be denied access to education on any ground be it financial status, geographical location, physical ability or disability, sex, culture and others.

Out-Of-School-Children in Nigeria

According to UNESCO's definition, out-of-school-children refer to children in the official primary school age range who are not enrolled in primary or secondary school. Out-of-school can further be described as children of compulsory school age range who never enrolled and those who left before completion (i.e. drop out). A range of factors can impact students' or parents' decision not to enroll their children in school or to let them drop out of school. This host of factors form barriers to education. Nigeria holds a horrible position of being out of school in the world. UNESCO in September 2023, put the number of out-of-school children in Nigeria at about 20 million being the highest number of out-of-school children in the world ranging from children between 6-18 years of age comprising both basic and secondary school-age children. They further assert that this number includes children who never attended school and

those who left school early. Most OOSCs at the primary level have never entered school, but most OOSCs of upper secondary age dropped out. Abdulsemiu (2022), asserts that the out-of-school children in Nigeria include girl-child in northern Nigeria, boy-child dropouts in the south-south and southeast regions, internally displaced children and Almajiri-Qur'anic and children from the nomadic communities who are predominantly found in the northern part of the country.

According to UNESCO (2023), Nigeria's OOS population accounts for about 15% of the global total. They further revealed that one in every three children is out of school in Nigeria and one in every five children out of school in the world is a Nigerian and only one in three adolescents eligible for senior secondary school are attending school. Cambridge Education (2021) further revealed that 86% are from rural areas and the poorest quintile and 66% of OOSC in Nigeria are in the northeast and northwest. These figures have been strongly disputed by the UBEC. According to UNESCO, the data is based on children aged 6-18 years ranging from primary to senior secondary, while UBEC's data is related to ages 6-11 (The Guardian, 2023). The argument as to whether the number is less than 20 million may not be necessary or hold water. It is the duty of every responsible government to ensure that no child is out of school, education is the right of every child.

The sympathetic historical review of out-of-school children in Nigeria as reported by the Guardian (2023), shows that the number has always been on the increase; 6.4million in 2000; 7.5million in 2010; 9.6million in 2020; and 13.5million in 2021. These perpetual massive increases in the number of out-of-school children in Nigeria are an indication that the country had fallen short of the global Education For All (EFA) by 2000 movement launched in 1990 and the Millennium Development

Goals for providing free and compulsory universal education for all children by 2015 launched in 2000. This is a wake-up call that if the government doesn't strategies and take pragmatic steps toward the reduction of out-of-school children, achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goal target by 2030 might be a mirage. This makes it imperative to investigate further into the causes of out-of-school children in Nigeria and profile suitable methods of tackling the menace.

Barriers to Access to Education in Nigeria

Most reasons why children drop out of school appear to be beyond their control and are traceable to the ineptitude of the government and society. A critical observation as to why children drop out of school revealed that factors that contribute to the incidence of out-of-school children include but are not limited to insecurity/conflict, socio-cultural norms, poverty, lack of accurate data and planning, corruption, and poor quality of teaching. These 'demand and supply barriers' could lead to the state of never enrolled in school, delayed enrolment, or a school drop-out.

Insecurity Issues

No learning can take place under conflict and unsecured environment. In a report by UNESCO (2022), attacks on schools and abduction of school children together with unsafe basic infrastructure and facilities (e.g., classrooms, furniture, fencing,) were major reasons that kept children out of school. Most parents are not disposed to sending their children or wards to school as a result of terrorist attacks, kidnapping, the killing of students and teachers, and burning of schools by the Islamic militant group Boko Haram and the ISWAP (Islamic State in West African Province) in the North East. These forms of insecurity have led to the forceful flee of some teachers and children out of school in

and around Borno state. Another is the sit-at-home order by the group of Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), the havoc from unknown gunmen and Niger Delta militants in the southern part of Nigeria has also led to the closure of schools in the south for several months.

WFP (2021) reveals that in Adamawa, Borno and Yobe states, which are in the Northeastern part of Nigeria, over 2 million people reside in IDP camps and host communities. We could also recall that many students were abducted from Chibok Girls Secondary School in Borno, likewise Dapchi Girls Secondary School in Adamawa and many others. In a report in News Flash Punch (2023, 17th December), a member of the House of Representatives, Ahmed Jaha, representing Chibok, Domboa and Gwoza Federal Constituency said that no fewer than 87 Chibok girls were still in Boko Haram's captivity. Boko Haram terrorists attacked the Government Girls Secondary School in Chibok and kidnapped 276 girls on April 14, 2014. Fifty-seven of the schoolgirls escaped immediately after jumping from the trucks on which they were being transported, while others were rescued by the military. Furthermore, according to Odeyemi (2021) in Ikiyei et al (2022), not less than 600 teachers have been murdered in Borno state, at least more than 19,000 teachers have been displaced and well over 1,200 schools destroyed by terrorists.

Poverty

Poverty is the biggest barrier to access to education, exacerbated by exorbitant school fees and other costs of education. Although public Basic education is declared free in Nigeria, research has shown that in the actual sense, some fees are involved, such as registration fees, cost of uniforms, writing materials and textbooks, excursion fees, teaching aid fees, examination fees, Parent-Teachers Association (PTA) levy and other

miscellaneous fees such as fees for sanitary materials, furniture, sports, security, and others. According to Yahaya (2018), students often drop out of school because of financial problems, the loss of a parent or sponsor, and the quest to get a job to sustain life and could not work and go to school at the same time. Such student may decide to drop out of school or refuse to further their education to the next level. Bakari (2013) observed that Parents/ guardians who have low-income status prefer to educate the male child alone as they will be the future breadwinners. Even though most Nigerians may be aware of the importance of education to the future of male and female children, they lack the financial capacity to send them to schools. An average Nigerian family especially in the rural areas is living in abject poverty, given this, most parents see sending their wards to school as an added burden to the already over-stressed family income.

Culture and Gender Issues

The cultural norms of northern and southern Nigeria that place a low value on education for girls and boys' children respectively contribute to the high rate of school dropout in Nigeria. According to Chege et al., (2008) in northern Nigeria, public schools are considered un-Islamic, too Westernized, and /or corrupting, especially girls. In addition, Okojie (2008) identified that one of their beliefs is that educating a girl may lead to their marrying late and running the risk of being childless. Okojie (2008) also added that it is believed that any economic benefit from formal education will go to the husband's home and the demand by Hausa – Fulani in particular that girls should be sent to hawk goods as a means of strengthening self-reliance and meeting potential suitors. In addition, the tradition of early marriage, especially for adolescents below the age of 18 in rural areas of the northern part of the country affects enrolment and retention of

children in schools. The Federal Ministry of Education FME (2005), asserts that pregnancy is a major cause of dropout, especially at JSS level, 18% of females were married before the age of 15, and 40% were married by the age of 18. Cases of early marriage are much higher among poorer, rural households in the North and these contribute to out-of-school children in Nigeria. This practice is an infringement on the rights of children. It is the right of every child to be educated and none should be denied. In a like manner, home chores and sibling-care keep children out of school especially when parents are poor or dead. According to Bakari (2013), home chores affect both boys and girls but girls generally more, especially in poorer, more rural households. British Council (2012) opined that girls often have to look after younger siblings and /or care for sick relatives either because they have been orphaned or because the mother needs to go out to work. In the same vein, Yahaya (2018) noted that parents who are petty traders or farmers involve their children in their occupation thus limiting their participation in school.

Inadequate School /Classroom

Lack of comprehensive data on Out-of-School-Children, poor funding and corruption limits the reach and impact of interventions by government and stakeholders despite an impressive drive to increase the number of schools from primary to tertiary education across the country in recent years, the federal and state government has not been able to achieve a lot as there are still overcrowded classrooms and long distance to school which are indicators of insufficient educational infrastructure to accommodate learners. This simply means that there are fewer public schools compared to the growing population. It is imperative to know that as the population grows, many more settlements are established, if no new

schools are built, equity and accessibility to public schools become a major challenge to the achievement of Sustainable Development in Nigeria. According to Punch (2023, September 19), UBEC revealed that Nigeria needs 20,000 new schools and 907,769 classrooms to be able to absorb the growing of out of school children in the country. The chronic underfunding and improper budgetary allocation to education, population explosion and inefficient use of available resources perpetuates the Out-of-School phenomenon. Exploratory data analysis and empirical estimation revealed the facts that a higher number of rural-dwelling children do not go to school as compared to the children living in the urban areas in Nigeria and the Northeast geo-political zone has the largest percentage of Out-of-School-Children in Nigeria.

Child Trafficking Issues

Millions of children and adolescent boys and girls in Nigeria are victims of human trafficking for sexual exploitation, forced labour, and other forms of exploitation. The educational implications of this take an immense toll on individuals and communities. Street and trafficked children lack access to education because they are engaged in other activities like domestic services, trading and begging during school hours. In addition, according to the Women's Consortium of Nigeria, WOCON (2023) Traffickers force internally trafficked children into labour such as shop attendance, catering service, head loading, bakery-hands, hawking and prostitution. The conditions of labour are exploitative and slave-like. WOCON (2023) further stressed that as domestic workers, for example, the children are subjected to about 12- 18 hours of cleaning, baby care, cooking and other forms of household chores and hard work. Such children are the first to get up in the morning and the last to go to bed in the

household. Most of the children are denied any form of formal or vocational training. These affect both boys and girls.

Children are trafficked – generally from rural to urban areas. Aronowicz (2006) noted that females are often trafficked into domestic service, street trading and sexual exploitation whereas males are engaged in a greater range of activities, including street trading, agriculture, mining, petty crime and the drug trade. The adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in September 2015 renewed political commitment to combat Trafficking in Persons and protect victims. Street and trafficked children also contribute to the number of out-of-school children in Nigeria.

Poor Quality of Teaching

Poor quality of teaching kills motivation, affects learning outcomes and destroys the needed academic performance to progress to the next level of education thereby contributing to the rate of school dropout in Nigeria. According to Oni et al., (2016), the quality of any educational system is mostly assessed by the performance of the system's products. Any system of education that cannot produce an individual who is useful to themselves, and their society and cannot meet up with global challenges is defective. The fact is that a greater percentage of the products of students who attend secondary education in Nigeria cannot make it to tertiary level as a result of poor academic performance and those who scale through cannot stand on their own, nor are they employable, talk less of contributing to the achievement of the national goals and objectives. This bothers on insufficient supply of trained teachers to give quality education, inefficient teacher recruitment and deployment, and lack of attractive salary and benefits packages to motivate,

attract and retain talented teachers. Others are poor capacity building or in-service training arrangements for teachers to be equipped with new ideas, knowledge, modern skills and methods necessary for the development of their profession and further enhance their role. Furthermore, the inadequate proper and regular supervision by government and stakeholders has led to a lack of direction, guidance and control needed to keep them working to plan, Supervision they say; inspires efficiency among workers.

To add sore to injury, research has shown that school duties – particularly cleaning done by students during school hours – can take up much of the school day in Nigeria, impacting negatively on educational quality. Another is corporal punishment – although it is now forbidden in schools, but only allowed to be administered by the head teacher, excessive corporal punishment is still widely reported and is often for offenses for which children are not directly responsible (e.g. non-payment of PTA levies) (Yahaya et al., 2024). It has been found that corporal punishment results in emotional distress, absenteeism and dropout. Alternative or complementary punishments, however, are often still physically humiliating and take time from learning.

Almajiri and Nomadic Lifestyle

“Almajiri” is a Hausa word derived from the Arabic word ‘*Al-muhajirun*’, meaning migrants. In northern Nigeria, it refers to persons who travel far from home in search of Islamic knowledge. This group lacks conventional classroom knowledge. Almajiri children account for the majority of schoolchildren in the north. The Federal Government of Nigeria under former President Goodluck Jonathan in an attempt to mainstream the Almajiri system launched the Almajiri model school in Jigawa state and commissioned the first 100 sets of schools across Nigeria on April 10th,

2012 in Sokoto State to integrate the Almajiri system into basic education system, but this has not created the needed impact as a result lack of commitment from the government. Another major contributing factor to the rate of out-of-school children is the nomadic lifestyle. The children of nomadic pastorals, migrant fisher folks, migrant farmers, hunters, etc. due to their lifestyles and means of livelihood, are unable to have access to the conventional educational programme. Policy to address the educational needs of nomadic groups by providing special education has been adopted at federal and state levels but receives minimal financial and institutional support (Pinnock 2020). Despite their major contribution to the Nigerian economy, the nomadic pastoralists are some of the most socially disadvantaged groups in the country, with especially poor access to education and this stands as a challenge to the achievement of inclusive education.

Implication of Out-of-School Children on Sustainable Development

The purpose of every education is human development. According to UNDP (1990) in Charity et al., (2020) human development has been defined as the process of enlarging people’s choices and improving human capabilities, freedoms, guaranteed human rights and self-respect so they can live a long, and healthy life, have access to education and a decent standard of living, participate in their community and the decisions that affect their lives. Education is the key to a full and productive life for the child and the progress of the nation. Education is the foundation for children’s future well-being and sustainable development of any nation. The most frequently used definition of Sustainable development is from the Brundtland Report of 1987 which says; “Sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present (people) without

compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. In other words, it is improving the quality of life of the present generation without excessive use or abuse of natural resources, so that they can be preserved for the next generation. Sustainable Development is often broken out into three constituent parts namely, economic sustainability socio-political sustainability, and environmental sustainability.

Economic Sustainability

Education plays a critical role in the economic development of any nation. It is the pivot upon which human capacity development is enhanced for the benefit of the present and future generations. The economic and technological advancement in every nation cannot be disassociated from the educational attainment of its citizens. That is why Psacharopoulos & Patrinos (2004) acknowledged that an educated workforce is crucial to technological innovation and structural transformation. Education provides the child with vocational skills, which leads to employment opportunities that increase creativity and productivity and ensure economic growth in any given society. According to Victor (2014), education can be used as a tool to put in place a favourable environment that will usher in a diversified economic prosperity that would bring about the realization of the dreams and aspirations of citizens. Lack of access to education imposes enormous costs on individual economic and technological advancement and the nation at large. It has a great impact on the immediate cycle flow and recycling of income in the family and nation. It leads to unemployment, poor investment in business, loss of income and reduced tax revenues accruing to the government due to low-income earnings as a result of being out of school. This may in turn affect the building and maintenance of public

facilities like road constructions, hospitals, libraries, railway lines, and other infrastructure which depend on income from tax. The implication of being out of school has a negative net fiscal contribution to society. However, the economic costs over time of inadequate trained manpower are low productivity and income which affect the development of any nation. Furthermore, the likelihood of poverty and lack of career opportunities make out-of-school individuals to be prone to crimes and substance abuse. A child develops self-confidence when he or she has the basic knowledge and skills that make him valuable to the society through which he earns a living legitimately. Education offers self-confidence for an individual to resist the temptation of unscrupulous or evil-minded people.

Social-Political Sustainability

Educational attainment cannot be disentangled from social well-being. Illiteracy can be a major cause of poverty, abuse, exploitation, poor health and increased rate of mortality in any nation. No wonder, Mahuta (2017) asserted that schools as social institution possesses the power to shape the character of individuals and that of the community as a whole. The role of education is to eradicate illiteracy by equipping young learners with the required knowledge, skills and attitudes to cope with everyday societal issues to reduce both personal and state insecurity and improve their social well-being and others. No nation can attain sustainable development with a high rate of illiteracy. Individuals who acquire certain skills such as reading, writing and numeracy are more likely to have a better future than their counterpart who lacks these skills. This is because effective communication and interaction are necessary ingredients to participation in politics, economics and all other forms of social activities relevant to the development of the society. Ikiyei et al

(2022) observed that education increases lifetime income and expands the labour market potential of an individual. Many who could not complete their education may grow to become permanent liabilities to their relatives and society as they have fewer opportunities for employment in society. Furthermore, even when they are employed, the tendency that they would be placed on far lower salaries that can hardly sustain them and their dependants is glaringly inevitable.

Education provides the learner the enlightenment about his or her rights. This includes both social and political rights. Through education, we can achieve a free and democratic society. A society where the individual is allowed to enjoy his rights and privileges as provided for by the law of the land. The role of education in this regard is to nurture the individual to appreciate the legitimate demand for freedom in his life. That is why Victor (2014) acknowledged that an individual must be educated to know that he is a member of a social unit and as such, he must take the interest or freedom of others into account while exercising his freedom. Through this also, we can eradicate child labour, child trafficking, and other form of child abuse from the society at large. Again, education as submitted by Adeyinka (2014) is a tool for liberating the individual from the shackles of ignorance to the world of ideas, knowledge and imagination. Education promotes a sense of respect, tolerance, cooperation, and sharing. In the same vein, out-of-school children are a threat to any country's political well-being as the illiterate and poorly educated citizens of the society who are unemployed could be used by some influential members of the society to perpetrate crimes like political conflict, ethnic and religious conflict, kidnapping to cause unrest that could scare potential voters before and during the election, to disrupt the political process. Education can help sanitise the electoral process from vote

buying, ballot snatching, kidnapping of officials or opponents, and all forms of political thuggery. That is why Aghedo & Eke (2013) submit that education can dismantle the unscrupulous elites and political class who use out-of-school children and adolescents as their political thugs to commit atrocities among the unsuspecting public.

Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability is an inseparable part of the concept of Sustainable Development. According to Ziaul & Shwei (2022) ensuring an environmentally sustainable society for the common benefits of present and future generations is indispensable. Practicing environmental sustainability helps create a healthy planet for the current generations and saves natural resources for future ones. No nation can achieve sustainable development today without a sustainable environment that promotes economic and social well-being. Ironically, the struggle for socio-economic growth and development over the years has been the main cause of environmental degradation today in developing countries, particularly Nigeria. Most of the environmental problems encountered by developing countries include carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission, hazardous pollution, climate change, global warming, floods, droughts, deforestation, excessive and less rainfall crises, scarcity of food, water and other natural resources which are all consequences of misuse and overconsumption of natural resources, and loss of biodiversity.

Studies have shown that environmental degradation is rising worldwide and one of the major ways of combating it is through education policies and poverty reduction. This is because human activities in the name of development are the main reasons for destroying the environment and natural

resources. Most citizens who are uneducated and unemployed largely depend on illegal means of abstracting available natural resources with little or no consideration for its effect on the present and future generations. No wonder, Ziaul & Shwei (2022) acknowledged that irresponsible human activities primarily hinder sustainable development progress, which is essential for present and future generations. Therefore, adopting flexible environmental coping strategies with mass-level awareness creation to create environmental consciousness is imperative and providing access to education is key to embracing the environmental sustainability approach necessary to ensure sustainable development in Nigeria.

Recommendations

To remedy the challenges of out-of-school-children in Nigeria for the achievement of sustainable development; the government and stakeholders should:

1. reduce the cost of education by eliminating school fees at all levels of education, providing cash transfers, strengthening the fight against poverty in the land, creating a more conducive environment for businesses to thrive, and creating employment for unemployed parents to afford the education of their children;
2. take pragmatic steps to address cases of terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, and other form of insecurity in Nigeria;
3. come up with a national policy to address the issue of Almajiri and nomadic children being the majority of out-of-school children in Nigeria;
4. increase budgetary allocation to education to cater to teachers and establish adequate schools and classrooms in every village and locality for easy accessibility to learners no matter where they live;

5. make and implement strong laws that guide against child trafficking and all forms of child abuse like sexual abuse, early marriage, and corporal punishment, and address socio-cultural norms and beliefs that prevent school enrolment;
6. put in place adequate monitoring mechanisms for full implementation of educational policies and programmes designed and formulated to improve education in Nigeria; and
7. put in place an intensive enlightenment campaign strategy to educate the public and create awareness about the importance of education for the well-being of present and future generations.

Conclusion

The rising number of out-of-school children in Nigeria has a great implication for the achievement of sustainable development in Nigeria. A child attends school to acquire education to fit into the society he belongs to. He does not only benefit from school when it comes to knowledge, attitudes, skill development, employment opportunities, career advancement, and income, but his immediate community receives benefits from his education as well. There is a popular saying that “You cannot reap where you did not sow”, every child has the potential once adequately nurtured to contribute to the development of society and the nation in general. Communities with higher rates of educated citizens tend to be healthier and have higher rates of economic growth and stability, political development, lower crime rate and exploitation, and greater equality that promotes development and sustainability. Lack of access to education may have multiple implications for individuals and society including economic, socio-political and environmental implications.

References

- Abdulsemiu, M. (2022) Despite the alternative intervention, the number of out-of-school children keeps rising in Nigeria. Retrieved on 4th May 2023 from <https://www.thecable.ng/despite-alternative-intervention-number-of-out-of-schoolchildren-keeps-rising-in-nigeria/amp>
- Adeyinka, A (2014). Active teachers, passive learners: Reflections on Paulo Freire's pedagogy and related works. *Niger Delta Journal of Education*, 6 (1 & 2), 1- 8.
- Aghedo, I. and Eke, S.J. (2013). From Alms to Arms: The Almajiri Phenomenon and Internal Security in Northern Nigeria. *The Korean Journal of Policy Studies*; 28 (3); 97 -123.
- Aronowicz, I., Castle, S. & Diallo, V. (2010). Too often in silence: a report on school-based violence in West and Central Africa. Dakar: UNICEF, plan west Africa, save the children Sweden, west Africa, action aid. (s-or)
- Bakari, s., (2004). Gender and equity in teacher education: a case study from Nigeria. Unpublished PhD thesis. University of Sussex, UK. (p&e: mix; stats, obs, fgp, int-I, dr, and personal narrative)
- British Council, (2012). Gender in Nigeria report 2012: improving the lives of women and girls in Nigeria (2nd edition). Abuja British Council Nigeria.
- Cambridge Education. (2021). Investment Case for Out-of-School Children in Nigeria. Cambridge: UNICEF.
- Charity, N. O, Emenike, J. A. Doma, A., & Akinsola, M, O (2020) Out of School Children: Enhancing Factors and Consequences for Sustainable Development in North Central Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 8, (10), 804-811
- Chege, F., Zakariya, J.O., Okojie, C., and Aregbeyen, O., (2008). Girls' Education Project (GEP) Evaluation Report. Abuja: UNICEF (P&E; eval-f)
- Fafunwa, B. A. (2008). History of Education London George. Allen & Urwin
- Federal Ministry of Education, (2014), National Policy on Education. Abuja: NERDC
- Federal Government of Nigeria (2005): Nigeria's Millennium Development Goals Report, Abuja: National Planning Commission.
- Guardian (2022). Nigeria now has 20 million out-of-school children, says UNESCO. Retrieved on 4th May 2023 from <https://guardian.ng/news/nigeria-now-has-20-million-of-school-children-sas-unesco/>
- Guardian (2023, 19th February). Tackling the menace of out-of-school in Nigeria <https://guardian.ng/sunday-magazine/tackling-menace-of-out-of-school-children-in-Nigeria/amp/>
- Ikiyei P.K., Donkemezuo I., Precious M., Seribofa T.I. (2022), Out-of-School Children in Nigeria: A Creation by Society and its Implications for Nation Building. *British Journal of Contemporary Education* 2(2), 17-32. DOI:10.52589/BJCETENR2EIA
- Mahuta, M. G. (2007). An Introduction to Sociological Foundation of Education. Calabar.
- Musa Y. et al., (2019). Achieving Functional Teacher Education in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects In A Fragile Economy. *Zuba Journal of Arts and Social Science* (ZUJASS) 4(1), 35.
- News Flash (Punch) (2023, 17th

- December) 87 Chibok girls still in Boko Haram captivity - rep. <https://ngnewsflash.com/87-chibok-girls-still-in-boko-haram-captivity-rep/>
- Oni, J. O. et al., (2016) Enhancing access to and quality of basic education through head teachers' leadership functions. Lagos
- Pinnock, H. (2020). Inclusive Education in Nigeria: Policy Progress Weakened by Financing. UNESCO Global Education Monitoring Report.
- PUNCH (2023, 19th September) Nigeria needs 20000 schools to absorb out-of-school children - UBEC <https://punchng.com/nigeria-needs-20000-schools-to-absorb-out-of-school-children-ubec/?amp>
- PUNCH (2023, 22nd September) Out of School estimate no longer relevant – UBEC <https://punchng.com/out-of-school-children-estimate-no-longer-relevant-ubec/?amp>
- Psacharopolous, G., & Patrinos, H. A. (2004). Returns to Education: A further update. *Education Economics*, 12(2), 111 - 134.
- UBEC (2018) Personnel Audit and Digest of Basic Education Statistics in Nigeria United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals Report (2022). Retrieved on 11thMay 2023 from <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/goal-06/>
- UNESCO (2015), Sustainable Development Goal 4 and its targets. Retrieved on 13th April, 2023 from <https://en.unesco.org/education2030-sdg4/targets>
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2015). Out-of-School Children and Adolescents in Asia and the Pacific: Left Behind on the Road to Learning Opportunities for All.
- UNESCO (1994), World Declaration on Education For All And Framework For Action To Meet Basic Learning Needs.
- United Nations (2015) Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development. United Nations General Assembly.
- Victor, E. A., (2014), Introduction to Philosophy of Education. Revised and Expanded Edition. Winworld Press F.C.T Abuja.
- WFP (World Food Programme) (2021), *North-eastern Nigeria Emergency*. World Food Programme. Retrieved from <https://www.wfp.org/emergencies/nigeria-emergency>
- WOCON (Women's Consortium of Nigeria) (2023) newsletter: Trafficking in Nigeria <https://www.womenconsortiumofnigeria.org?q=content/nigeria>
- Yahaya, M. A. (2018) Effects of Parental Socioeconomic Status On Students' Academic Achievement in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. Unpublished B(Ed) project, University of Abuja, Nigeria.
- Yahaya, M.A, Yusuff, M.B, & Lawal O.T (2024), The Role of Basic Education For the Achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG4) *UNIOSUN Journal of Teaching and Learning* (UJTL) 4(1).
- Ziaul, I. M. & Shuwei, W. (2022). "Environmental Sustainability: A Major Component of Sustainable Development". *International Journal of Environmental, Sustainability, and Social Sciences*, 4 (2), 620 - 627.